

The Role of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) in the Management of High-Grade Gliomas

Mustafa Farooq BSc^{1*}, Rahul Patel BSc¹,

Maheen Farooq MSc², Mehul Mehra MD³

Affiliation: ¹Wellstar Medical College of Georgia, Augusta, Georgia, USA

²Edward Via College of Medicine

³Wellstar Medical College of Georgia, Department of Neurosurgery, Augusta, Georgia, USA

* Correspondence: mufarooq@augusta.edu

Abstract

This paper explores the role of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) in managing high-grade gliomas, particularly glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), through non-invasive electric field-based therapy. It highlights how TTFields disrupt mitosis in rapidly dividing tumor cells by targeting key proteins, such as tubulin and septin, involved in spindle formation during cell division. The therapy selectively induces mitotic arrest and apoptosis, sparing non-dividing healthy cells, thus minimizing side effects. Preclinical evidence supports TTFields' efficacy in disrupting cancer cell division and enhancing the effects of chemotherapy, particularly temozolomide. The EF-14 trial established TTFields as a standard therapy for newly diagnosed GBM, showing significant improvements in overall and progression-free survival compared to chemotherapy alone. Real-world data from the PRiDe registry corroborate these findings, demonstrating similar survival benefits and a favorable safety profile. Challenges include patient compliance due to the device's daily usage requirements and cost-related barriers. Ongoing research explores the combination of

TTFields with immunotherapy, radiation, and novel therapeutic agents, as well as its potential applications in other solid tumors. Future studies may focus on improving patient adherence, expanding therapeutic combinations, and refining device technology for broader cancer treatment applicability.

Keywords

High-grade gliomas, Tumor Treating Fields, TTFields, glioblastoma, non-invasive therapy, electric fields, cancer treatment

Introduction

High-grade gliomas, particularly glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), are among the most lethal primary brain tumors, characterized by rapid growth, infiltrative nature, and resistance to standard therapies. Despite advances in surgical resection, radiation therapy, and chemotherapy, the prognosis for patients with high-grade gliomas remains poor, with median survival often less than 15 months following diagnosis. Given the dismal outcomes associated with these tumors, there is a critical need for innovative therapeutic approaches.

Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) have emerged as a promising non-invasive modality designed to enhance therapeutic outcomes. TTFields are low-intensity, alternating electric fields delivered to the tumor site through transducer arrays placed on the scalp. These electric fields are specifically designed to disrupt mitosis, the process of cell division, thereby inhibiting tumor growth and progression. Since its approval by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 2015 for treating newly diagnosed glioblastoma, TTFields have been the subject of extensive research aimed at understanding their mechanisms of action, clinical efficacy, and potential applications in combination

with other therapies (Verhaak et al., 2010; Brennan et al., 2013).

This review article provides a comprehensive overview of the role of TTFields in managing high-grade gliomas, examining their mechanisms of action, clinical applications, current challenges, and future directions.

Mechanism of Action of Tumor Treating Fields

Selective electrokinetic Disruption of Mitosis

Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) exert their therapeutic effects primarily through the electrokinetic disruption of mitosis, a process that is critical for cell division in rapidly proliferating cancer cells. TTFields deliver alternating electric fields at intermediate frequencies, typically around 200 kHz, with low intensities of approximately 1-3 V/cm, which are specifically targeted to the tumor site. The electric fields generated by TTFields interact with highly polarized and charged intracellular structures, particularly molecules like tubulin and septin, which are integral components of the mitotic spindle. The mitotic spindle is a complex, dynamic structure essential for chromosome segregation during mitosis. Tubulin polymerizes to form microtubules, while septin is involved in the stabilization of the cytokinetic bridge during cell division (Kiyomitsu & Boerner, 2021; Salvador et al., 2023).

The alternating nature of these electric fields induces dielectrophoretic forces, which act on dipole moments within the charged molecules. These forces generate disruptive mechanical stresses on the tubulin and septin molecules, impairing their ability to organize into functional mitotic spindles. Specifically, the dielectrophoretic

effects of TTFields interfere with the proper alignment and assembly of microtubules, impeding their ability to attach to kinetochores on chromosomes (Zheng et al., 2022; Ballo et al., 2023). This leads to improper segregation of chromosomes and results in mitotic catastrophe, where cells become arrested in mitosis due to the failure of normal spindle function (Sun et al., 2021).

Additionally, TTFields cause abnormal multipolar divisions, wherein cancer cells attempt to divide without forming a proper bipolar mitotic spindle. These multipolar divisions increase genomic instability, further driving cancer cell death. As a result of the disrupted mitotic process, cells are unable to complete cytokinesis, which leads to mitotic arrest and subsequent apoptosis (Fishman et al., 2023).

A hallmark of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) therapy is its selective cytotoxicity towards rapidly dividing tumor cells, providing a significant therapeutic advantage by minimizing collateral damage to healthy tissue. The differential sensitivity between malignant and normal cells is based on the distinct biophysical properties of dividing cells and the precise tuning of electric fields to target the mitotic process.

Aggressive malignancies like high-grade gliomas exhibit uncontrolled and frequent cell division. TTFields exploit this characteristic by delivering alternating electric fields at an optimal frequency. This frequency is specifically tuned to interfere with the mitotic machinery in dividing cells, such as the assembly and disassembly of microtubules, critical for chromosome segregation. Tubulin is particularly susceptible to disruption by the alternating electric fields, due to its polar nature,

leading to cell cycle arrest and apoptosis (Fishman et al., 2023; Stupp et al., 2017).

In contrast, healthy cells in the adult brain, which are either quiescent or divide infrequently, are largely spared by TTFIELDS. Non-dividing cells lack the dynamic mitotic machinery necessary for division and thus remain unaffected by the electric fields. Studies have shown that non-dividing cells are minimally disrupted by TTFIELDS, as the dielectrophoretic forces generated are insufficient to interfere with their non-mitotic processes (Stupp et al., 2017). Furthermore, clinical trials, such as the pivotal EF-14 study, have demonstrated the safety and efficacy of TTFIELDS, as can be read below (Stupp et al., 2017).

Preclinical Evidence

Preclinical studies have played a critical role in elucidating the mechanism and efficacy of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS). Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models have consistently demonstrated that TTFIELDS induce significant disruption of rapidly proliferating tumor cells. The disruption of microtubule dynamics directly results in mitotic catastrophe, characterized by failed cytokinesis, chromosomal misalignment, and ultimately apoptosis

In vitro studies using glioblastoma cell lines have shown that the application of TTFIELDS disrupts the normal function of the mitotic spindle apparatus by interfering with the organization and assembly of tubulin, a key structural protein in microtubules.

In addition to these direct cytotoxic effects, TTFIELDS have been shown to exert a synergistic effect when used in combination with standard chemotherapeutic agents, particularly temozolomide. Preclinical data suggest that TTFIELDS sensitize tumor cells to the effects of

temozolomide, a DNA-alkylating agent used as the standard of care in glioblastoma treatment. In models of glioblastoma, TTFIELDS disrupted the DNA repair mechanisms that are upregulated in response to temozolomide-induced damage, thereby increasing the susceptibility of tumor cells to apoptosis. This combined approach of TTFIELDS and temozolomide has been shown to significantly prolong survival in animal models (Ballo et al., 2023). Additionally, the use of TTFIELDS in preclinical xenograft models resulted in marked reductions in tumor growth rates and increased survival times compared to controls, supporting the hypothesis that TTFIELDS enhance the cytotoxic effects of conventional therapies (Stupp et al., 2017).

Moreover, *in vivo* studies in rodent glioma models have demonstrated that TTFIELDS reduce tumor volume and slow disease progression without causing significant toxicity to surrounding healthy tissues (Salvador et al., 2023). These animal models mirror the selective action of TTFIELDS seen in clinical trials, where the alternating electric fields primarily target rapidly dividing tumor cells while sparing normal brain tissue. Importantly, the preclinical findings underscore that the effectiveness of TTFIELDS is dependent on continuous exposure to electric fields for a sustained period, typically around 18-24 hours per day. Such continuous application has been shown to maximize mitotic disruption and induce higher rates of tumor cell death (Giladi et al., 2017).

In summary, preclinical evidence provides compelling support for the use of TTFIELDS as an effective modality in cancer therapy. Its ability to disrupt microtubule dynamics and enhance the efficacy of standard chemotherapies, such as temozolomide, positions TTFIELDS as a valuable tool in the treatment of aggressive malignancies like glioblastoma. These findings from both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies have laid the groundwork for

the successful integration of TTFIELDS into clinical practice, as reflected by the improved survival outcomes in patients receiving TTFIELDS treatment (Fishman et al., 2023; Ballo et al., 2023).

Evidence from Clinical Trials

The clinical efficacy of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) in the management of high-grade gliomas, particularly glioblastoma multiforme (GBM), has been well-established through multiple pivotal clinical trials over the past decade.

EF-14 Trial: Establishing TTFIELDS as Standard Care for Newly Diagnosed Glioblastoma

The EF-14 trial was a pivotal phase III clinical study that established Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) as part of the standard treatment for newly diagnosed glioblastoma patients. This multicenter trial enrolled 695 patients who were randomized to receive either maintenance temozolomide alone or TTFIELDS in combination with temozolomide following surgery and radiation therapy. The results were groundbreaking, showing a significant improvement in both progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) in the TTFIELDS group. Median PFS increased from 4.0 months with temozolomide alone to 6.7 months with TTFIELDS (Stupp et al., 2017). Moreover, the median OS in the TTFIELDS group was 20.9 months compared to 16.0 months in the control group, reflecting a clear survival benefit.

The trial also demonstrated that the two-year survival rate increased from 29% to 43% with the addition of TTFIELDS, confirming its efficacy as an adjunctive therapy (Ballo et al., 2023).

Importantly, subgroup analyses revealed that patients with poor prognostic factors, such as those with unmethylated MGMT promoter status, also

benefited from TTFIELDS. The trial's findings were instrumental in gaining regulatory approval for TTFIELDS in newly diagnosed glioblastoma and have been widely integrated into clinical practice due to its tolerable safety profile, with skin irritation being the most common adverse event (Anadkat et al., 2023).

EF-11 Trial: Evaluating TTFIELDS as Monotherapy for Recurrent Glioblastoma

The EF-11 trial was another critical phase III study, but it focused on evaluating the efficacy of TTFIELDS as a monotherapy for patients with recurrent glioblastoma. The trial included 237 patients who had previously failed standard therapies, including surgery, radiotherapy, and chemotherapy. Patients were randomized to receive either TTFIELDS alone or the best available physician's choice of chemotherapy. The results showed that TTFIELDS were non-inferior to chemotherapy in terms of overall survival, with a median OS of 6.6 months in the TTFIELDS group compared to 6.0 months in the chemotherapy group (Stupp et al., 2012).

One of the key takeaways from the EF-11 trial was that TTFIELDS demonstrated a more favorable safety profile, with far fewer systemic side effects compared to chemotherapy. While the response rates were similar between the groups, the tolerability of TTFIELDS made it an appealing option for patients who had exhausted other treatment avenues (Vergote et al., 2023). The EF-11 trial helped to broaden the scope of TTFIELDS as a viable treatment for recurrent glioblastoma, particularly for patients with limited options.

PRiDe Registry: Real-World Data on TTFIELDS

The PRiDe registry (Patient Registry Dataset) is a significant source of real-world data that has corroborated the clinical trial outcomes for

TTFIELDS, particularly those from the EF-14 study. The registry includes over 1,200 patients with glioblastoma, many of whom were treated with TTFIELDS outside of a controlled clinical trial setting. The PRiDe registry demonstrated that patients with newly diagnosed glioblastoma had a median overall survival of 20.0 months, closely mirroring the outcomes seen in the EF-14 trial (Salvador et al., 2023).

For recurrent glioblastoma, the real-world data showed a median overall survival of 9.6 months, providing further evidence that TTFIELDS is a beneficial therapy even after initial disease progression. Additionally, the safety profile in the real-world setting was consistent with clinical trials, with skin irritation being the most common side effect. These findings highlight the practicality of TTFIELDS in everyday clinical settings and its accessibility for a broad patient population (Fishman et al., 2023).

Combination Therapies with TTFIELDS

Combination therapy approaches have been extensively explored to improve the therapeutic outcomes of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) in the treatment of high-grade gliomas. One of the most promising strategies has been the combination of TTFIELDS with chemotherapeutic agents such as temozolomide and lomustine, as well as radiation therapy. TTFIELDS have been shown to significantly enhance the permeability of the blood-brain barrier (BBB), which is a critical obstacle in delivering effective doses of chemotherapy to the brain. Preclinical studies demonstrated that TTFIELDS delocalize tight junction proteins in endothelial cells, leading to a reversible opening of the BBB, thus allowing for enhanced drug delivery (Salvador et al., 2023).

The combination of TTFIELDS with temozolomide has yielded particularly

compelling results. As mentioned, the landmark EF-14 trial demonstrated that patients receiving both TTFIELDS and temozolomide had a median overall survival (OS) of 20.9 months, compared to 16.0 months for those treated with temozolomide alone (Stupp et al., 2017). The combination of TTFIELDS with lomustine in preclinical models has shown to disrupt mitotic spindle formation more effectively, increasing cancer cell apoptosis when compared to monotherapy (Fishman et al., 2023). Additionally, TTFIELDS have been found to sensitize glioblastoma cells to the cytotoxic effects of these chemotherapeutic agents, further increasing treatment efficacy.

TTFIELDS have also shown synergy with radiation therapy. The alternating electric fields generated by TTFIELDS increase tumor cell susceptibility to radiation by enhancing the induction of double-strand DNA breaks, leading to more efficient tumor cell death. Studies have shown that the combined use of TTFIELDS and radiation therapy results in increased DNA damage, reduced tumor proliferation, and improved survival in preclinical glioblastoma models (Fishman et al., 2023). Furthermore, TTFIELDS disrupt the mitotic spindle assembly, enhancing the tumoricidal effects of radiation. The integration of TTFIELDS with radiation therapy offers a non-invasive, locoregional modality that can be administered without additional systemic toxicity, making it a viable option for long-term management of glioblastoma (Gondi et al., 2022).

The TRIDENT trial is an ongoing phase III trial designed to evaluate the early integration of TTFIELDS with radiation therapy and temozolomide in patients with newly diagnosed glioblastoma. Unlike the EF-14 trial, where TTFIELDS were started after radiation therapy, the TRIDENT trial aims to assess the benefits of initiating TTFIELDS during radiation therapy. Early results suggest that

combining TTFIELDS with radiation therapy may further enhance progression-free survival (PFS) and overall survival (OS) compared to the traditional approach of adding TTFIELDS after radiation (Ballo et al., 2023).

The trial also includes evaluations of quality of life and neurocognitive function to determine whether the early use of TTFIELDS introduces any additional side effects or compromises patient quality of life. If successful, this trial could redefine the timing of TTFIELDS in the treatment paradigm for glioblastoma, potentially offering improved outcomes without increasing the burden on patients (Vergote et al., 2023).

Challenges and Limitations

One of the primary challenges associated with TTFIELDS therapy is patient compliance. The treatment requires patients to wear transducer arrays on their scalps for at least 18 hours a day, which can be cumbersome and affect the quality of life. The device's portability and the need for frequent maintenance, such as changing the arrays and ensuring proper skin contact, can also be a deterrent for some patients. Skin irritation and dermatitis are among the most common adverse effects, reported in up to 52% of patients in the EF-14 trial (Stupp et al., 2017). Efforts are being made to develop more user-friendly devices and improve patient education and support to enhance adherence to TTFIELDS therapy.

TTFIELDS therapy is also associated with significant costs, which can limit its accessibility, especially in low- and middle-income countries. The device's high price and ongoing maintenance costs, combined with limited insurance coverage in some regions, present a substantial financial burden to patients and healthcare systems. There is a need for cost-effectiveness analyses to better understand

the long-term economic impact of TTFIELDS therapy and advocate for broader insurance coverage and subsidies to improve accessibility (González-Molina et al., 2022).

Heterogeneity in Tumor Response

The heterogeneity of glioblastoma and other high-grade gliomas poses another challenge to the effective use of TTFIELDS. Gliomas exhibit significant inter- and intra-tumor heterogeneity, which can affect treatment response. Some tumors may be more resistant to the effects of TTFIELDS due to variations in molecular and genetic profiles (Patel et al., 2014; Shearer et al., 2022).

Understanding the molecular characteristics that predict response to TTFIELDS is critical for optimizing patient selection and developing personalized treatment strategies. Ongoing research is focused on identifying biomarkers that can predict response to TTFIELDS and tailor therapy accordingly.

Future Directions in TTFIELDS Research

Ongoing research aims to develop next-generation TTFIELDS devices that are more comfortable, user-friendly, and effective. Future iterations of the device may incorporate flexible or wearable electronics that are less intrusive and easier to maintain, thereby improving patient compliance. Additionally, advancements in battery technology and device miniaturization could allow for more convenient and continuous use, even in more challenging environments (Moore et al., 2023).

Combination with Novel Therapeutic Agents

Researchers are also exploring the potential of combining TTFIELDS with novel therapeutic agents,

such as targeted therapies and immunotherapies. Preclinical studies have shown that TTFIELDS may enhance the efficacy of immune checkpoint inhibitors, such as anti-PD-1 and anti-PD-L1 antibodies, by promoting an immunogenic cell death pathway (Wen et al., 2010). Clinical trials are underway to evaluate these combinations' safety and efficacy, which may lead to new therapeutic protocols for high-grade gliomas.

While TTFIELDS have primarily been studied in the context of high-grade gliomas, there is growing interest in exploring their application in other cancer types. Preliminary studies suggest that TTFIELDS may be effective against various solid tumors, including non-small cell lung cancer, pancreatic cancer, and ovarian cancer (Friedman et al., 2021). Expanding the scope of TTFIELDS research could potentially benefit a broader range of cancer patients and open new avenues for non-invasive cancer therapies.

The HEPANOVA trial is a phase II trial exploring the efficacy of TTFIELDS in combination with the tyrosine kinase inhibitor sorafenib for patients with advanced hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC). While this trial is not focused on glioblastoma, it represents an important step in expanding the application of TTFIELDS beyond brain cancers. The preclinical data suggest that TTFIELDS could enhance the efficacy of sorafenib by disrupting cell division in rapidly proliferating tumor cells. If successful, the HEPANOVA trial could pave the way for future studies on TTFIELDS in various solid tumors, including pancreatic, ovarian, and lung cancers (Vergote et al., 2023).

Conclusion

Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) have demonstrated significant potential in the management of high-grade gliomas, particularly

glioblastoma, through their unique mechanism of action. By exploiting the rapid cell division characteristic of malignant gliomas, TTFIELDS selectively disrupt the mitotic processes essential for tumor growth. Preclinical studies have provided robust evidence supporting the ability of TTFIELDS to induce mitotic catastrophe and apoptosis in cancer cells, while sparing healthy, non-dividing cells. The efficacy of TTFIELDS has been further validated in clinical settings, where combination therapies, particularly with chemotherapeutic agents like temozolomide, have resulted in improved survival outcomes for glioblastoma patients.

The pivotal EF-14 trial firmly established TTFIELDS as part of the standard care for newly diagnosed glioblastoma, significantly extending both progression-free and overall survival in combination with temozolomide. Additionally, real-world data from the PRiDe registry have corroborated the clinical trial results, reinforcing the practicality and effectiveness of TTFIELDS in everyday clinical settings. However, despite these advancements, challenges remain, particularly concerning patient compliance, device-related adverse effects, and the high cost of treatment, which can limit accessibility in certain regions. Ongoing efforts aim to address these limitations by improving device design, enhancing patient education, and advocating for better insurance coverage.

Looking ahead, the potential for TTFIELDS to be integrated into broader cancer treatment paradigms is promising. Ongoing trials, such as the TRIDENT trial, are exploring the timing of TTFIELDS initiation, while others investigate its use in combination with novel therapies, including immunotherapies and targeted therapies. As research progresses, TTFIELDS may find application beyond glioblastoma, with trials like HEPANOVA exploring its efficacy in other solid tumors. As we

advance our understanding of TTFIELDS, it will become an increasingly valuable tool in the fight against aggressive malignancies, offering hope for improved survival and quality of life for patients with these challenging cancers.

References:

1. Anadkat M, Lacouture M, Friedman A, et al. Expert guidance on prophylaxis and treatment of dermatologic adverse events with Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) therapy in the thoracic region. *Frontiers in Oncology*. 2023;12.
 2. Ballo M, Conlon P, Lavy-Shahaf G, Kinzel A, Vymazal J, Rulseh A. Association of Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) therapy with survival in newly diagnosed glioblastoma: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Neurooncol*. 2023;164:1-9.
 3. Brennan C, Verhaak R, McKenna A, Campos B, Noushmehr H, Salama S, et al. The Somatic Genomic Landscape of Glioblastoma. *Cell*. 2013;155:462-477.
 4. Christakos S, Dhawan P, Verstuyf A, Verlinden L, Carmeliet G. Vitamin D: Metabolism, Molecular Mechanism of Action, and Pleiotropic Effects. *Physiol Rev*. 2016;96(1):365-408.
 5. Fishman H, Monin R, Dor-On E, Kinzel A, Haber A, Giladi M, et al. Tumor Treating Fields (TTFIELDS) increase the effectiveness of temozolomide and lomustine in glioblastoma cell lines. *J Neurooncol*. 2023;163:83-94.
 6. Friedman G, Johnston J, Bag A, Bernstock J, Li R, Aban I, et al. Oncolytic HSV-1 G207 Immunovirotherapy for Pediatric High-Grade Gliomas. *N Engl J Med*. 2021.
 7. Gondi V, Bauman G, Bradfield L, et al. Radiation Therapy for Brain Metastases: An ASTRO Clinical Practice Guideline. *Practical Radiation Oncology*. 2022;12:1-15.
 8. González-Molina V, Martí-Pineda A, González NE. Topical Treatments for Melasma and Their Mechanism of Action. *J Clin Aesthet Dermatol*. 2022;15(5):19-28.
 9. Kiyomitsu T, Boerner S. The Nuclear Mitotic Apparatus (NuMA) Protein: A Key Player for Nuclear Formation, Spindle Assembly, and Spindle Positioning. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology*. 2021;9. doi:10.3389/fcell.2021.649443.
 10. Moore M, Goldstein D, Hamm J, Figer A, Hecht J, Gallinger S, et al. Erlotinib Plus Gemcitabine Compared With Gemcitabine Alone in Patients With Advanced Pancreatic Cancer: A Phase III Trial of the National Cancer Institute of Canada Clinical Trials Group. *J Clin Oncol*. 2023;41:4714-20.
 11. Patel AP, Tirosh I, Trombetta JJ, Shalek A, Gillespie SM, Wakimoto H, et al. Single-cell RNA-seq highlights intratumoral
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- heterogeneity in primary glioblastoma. *Science*. 2014;344:1396-1401.
12. Salvador E, Köppl T, Hörmann J, Schönhärl S, Bugaeva P, Kessler A, et al. Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) Induce Cell Junction Alterations in a Human 3D In Vitro Model of the Blood-Brain Barrier. *Pharmaceutics*. 2023;15.
13. Shearer J, Castro JL, Lawson A, Maccoss M, Taylor RD. Rings in Clinical Trials and Drugs: Present and Future. *J Med Chem*. 2022;65:8699-712.
14. Stupp R, Taillibert S, Kanner A, Read W, Steinberg D, Lhermitte B, et al. Effect of Tumor-Treating Fields Plus Maintenance Temozolomide vs Maintenance Temozolomide Alone on Survival in Patients With Glioblastoma: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA*. 2017;318:2306–2316.
15. Sun M, Jia M, Ren H, et al. NuMA regulates mitotic spindle assembly, structural dynamics and function via phase separation. *Nature Communications*. 2021;12(1):1047. doi:10.1038/s41467-020-20522-3.
16. Verhaak R, Hoadley K, Purdom E, Wang V, Qi Y, Wilkerson M, et al. Integrated genomic analysis identifies clinically relevant subtypes of glioblastoma characterized by abnormalities in PDGFRA, IDH1, EGFR, and NF1. *Cancer Cell*. 2010;17(1):98-110.
17. Vergote I, Macarulla T, Hirsch F, et al. Tumor Treating Fields (TTFields) Therapy Concomitant with Taxanes for Cancer Treatment. *Cancers*. 2023;15.
18. Wen P, MacDonald DR, Reardon D, Cloughesy T, Sorensen A, Galanis E, et al. Updated response assessment criteria for high-grade gliomas: response assessment in neuro-oncology working group. *J Clin Oncol*. 2010;28(11):1963-72.
19. Zheng J, Tan Y, Liu X, et al. NAT10 regulates mitotic cell fate by acetylating Eg5 to control bipolar spindle assembly and chromosome segregation. *Cell Death & Differentiation*. 2022;29(4):846-860. doi:10.1038/s41418-021-00887-y.
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